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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE “QUVONCH” VARIABLE PROGRAM IN FAMILY NON-GOVERNMENTAL PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: This article highlights the provision of education in the preschool education system with due consideration to children’s abilities, interests, and needs. It also elucidates the purpose, objectives, and practical implementation of the “Quvonch” variable curriculum developed for family-based preschool educational organizations.

Key words and expressions: family-based preschool educational organization, variable curriculum, principles, formation of subjectivity, individual approach, integration.

Preschool age is a crucial stage in a child’s growth and development, characterized by a strong desire for self-expression, learning, and cognition. It is precisely during this period that the foundation for the development of a child’s personal qualities and intellectual potential is established. The earlier educational and upbringing processes begin in preschool age, the sooner their positive outcomes become evident, exerting a lasting influence on the child’s future life.

Preschool education and upbringing imply an individual approach to every child, respect for the child as a personality, moral and ethical development, and the organization of education in accordance with the child’s interests and needs.

A family-based preschool educational organization is a small-group institution established for the purpose of educating and upbringing children. In such institutions, children are nurtured in an environment that closely resembles a home setting.

In family-based non-governmental preschool educational organizations, children’s physical, intellectual, and moral abilities, which contribute to their future success in life, are developed through cognitive activities, exploration of the surrounding environment, speech development, listening to literary works, drawing, construction and design activities, physical exercises, and other forms of activity. These directions are harmonized and organized through integrated planning and are conducted in an engaging игровой manner. Since play corresponds to young children’s natural needs and interests, they enthusiastically repeat and easily assimilate the topics studied during play activities.

Within family-based non-governmental preschool educational organizations, the implementation of the “Quvonch” variable curriculum was planned with the aim of comprehensively developing preschool children intellectually, morally, aesthetically, and physically, as well as ensuring their high-quality preparation for school education through effective teaching and upbringing.

The purpose of the “Quvonch” variable curriculum is to provide every preschool child with quality preparation for school education by fostering well-mannered, intelligent, polite, self-confident, goal-oriented, independently thinking, physically healthy children who value national and universal values.

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The objectives of the “Quvonch” variable curriculum are to ensure the interrelation of all developmental domains established by the State Requirements for the Development of Early and Preschool-Aged Children; to promote children’s physical, socio-emotional, intellectual-cognitive, and creative development; to protect their health; and to create the necessary conditions for raising morally and spiritually mature individuals capable of independent and conscious living in the future.

The content of the “Quvonch” variable curriculum is based on the following principles:

The principles of the educational and upbringing process in family-based non-governmental preschool educational organizations include the following: scientificity, consistency, and adequacy.

- Recognizing childhood as a unique value.

Childhood is an important stage of life and human development. The distinctive feature of childhood is that children have a greater ability than adults to learn and change through educational experiences. Childhood is a significant period during which the child’s right to a happy childhood is recognized, and the foundations for development are established.

- Formation of subjectivity.

This includes respecting the dignity of the child, teaching individualization and cooperation within a group, satisfying the child’s conscious and justified needs, using psychological foundations of teaching, supporting the child’s abilities, choosing and applying democratic methods of upbringing, and relying on and promoting humanistic values.

- Taking into account the child’s rights, individuality, and developmental opportunities. All children are born with great potential and innate talents. Every child is unique and individual. All children have the right to protection and promotion of their health and well-being, as well as equal access to quality preschool education.

Children, including those with special needs, are recognized as active participants in the educational process. By choosing activities, participating in planning, and satisfying their natural curiosity for knowledge, they contribute to their own education and development.

- Ensuring the comprehensive development and well-being of every child. Preschool education is a harmonious process of care, education, and upbringing. It ensures the child’s development in all developmental domains and highlights the necessity of interconnection among these domains, as well as the importance of diverse and integrated learning opportunities in every area of development.

- Protecting and strengthening the child’s health and ensuring a safe environment. Children’s various needs, including the need for movement, should be met. Through active play and daily physical exercises, children develop their emotions, gross and fine motor skills, explore the surrounding world through movement, learn to manipulate objects, understand the abilities and responses of their bodies, and begin to care for themselves and adopt a healthy lifestyle.

- Learning and development through play.

Play is an important approach in preschool education. It brings joy and motivates children, enabling them to acquire new knowledge and skills and to explore themselves and the world around them. Preschool education recognizes the child’s right to play, the significance of play for

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children, and its pedagogical potential in supporting individual development, learning, and well-being.

- Cooperation of the preschool educational institution with the family, community, and school.

A child's well-being depends on family members and close relatives understanding the importance of preschool education. Children learn and develop better when parents and the local community are involved in the educational program and contribute to the educational and upbringing process.

- Recognition of national, historical, and cultural traditions, spiritual heritage, and respect for other cultures.

Children learn and develop more effectively when their national culture, language, and traditions are respected and acknowledged. The state curriculum is designed with consideration of national and regional cultural characteristics. Supporting a child's development in preschool education is a collective responsibility, and the director of the preschool educational institution is responsible for its implementation.

These principles form the foundation of the preschool education and upbringing process. They serve as guidelines for educators in planning and implementing the state curriculum and in making pedagogical and practical decisions regarding the education and development of every child.

When implementing the "Quvonch" variable program, it is necessary to aim at developing the following qualities in every child:

- creativity, imagination, and intelligence;
- the ability to think independently;
- the desire to identify problems and seek ways to solve them.

In order to improve the effectiveness of preschool education, it is important to pay special attention to involving parents in the process through cooperation. Parents are a child's first teachers. They always wish goodness for their children and hope they will become individuals who contribute to the prosperity of the Motherland and serve the interests of the people.

The educational and upbringing process requires great patience, kindness, and a scientifically grounded unified approach to child upbringing from both parents and educators. Properly organized upbringing prepares children to think independently and confidently step into adult life.

The practical implementation of the "Quvonch" variable program makes the educational process more interesting and effective and contributes to the development of children's abilities and interests.

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